

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE METHOD OF RE-NARRATION IN EDUCATING THE WORKS OF MIGUEL DE CERVANTES AND ISAJAN SULTON

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of the method of retelling the works of Medel De Cervantes. The impact of literary technologies and methods on the teaching of works of world literature and their importance to students are discussed. The uniqueness of world literature and national literary views and the significance of their retelling methods will be revealed in this article.

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ МЕТОДА ПЕРЕПОВЕДСТВИЯ В ПРОСВЕЩЕНИИ ТВОРЧЕСТВ МИГЕЛЯ ДЕ СЕРВАНТЕСА И ИСАДЖАНА СУЛТОНА

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ABSTRACT

В данной статье рассматривается значение метода пересказа произведений Меделя Де Сервантеса. Обсуждается влияние литературных технологий и методов на преподавание произведений мировой литературы и их значение для учащихся. В данной статье будет раскрыто своеобразие мировой литературы и национальных литературных воззрений, значение методов их пересказа.

In the personal development of students, it is also important to correctly express the technique of fluency and the forms of reaction to the thought expressed in practice. The

importance of using the method of retelling in the development of individual and personal style of the students, improvement of klaversa, speech technique is great. Work with examples of fiction, their presentation in front of the eyes of students should be carried out in a manner related to the method of retelling, using various videos, slides or scenes. "Therefore, during education and upbringing, we should give them understanding about the beauty of life, the peace of our country, our national traditions, and the family. For this, it is necessary to show children more different paces, read different stories, fairy tales, and describe their surroundings in a beautiful way. In preschool education organizations, this process is taught based on their age. It is appropriate to tell a story based on simpler pictures for children of a small group. When teaching storytelling, they are asked to tell familiar tales or newly learned stories.

Beautiful Dulcinea tells Sancho, who is our knight-at-arms, who pretends to be my beloved wife, the fulfiller of my dreams, that it is equal to the level of pride and honor that he continues to act in this way, to bear arms to an existing caballero. encourages. In many of Don Quixote's favorite works of chivalric legends, he thinks only that a sorceress known as Isplendea intervenes in the events. Amar Amadis of Gaul, the legitimate son of Islandia, continues with the adventures of the events, the barber's story told to him and the housekeeper willingly listening to these words. Concepts such as Archbishop Turen and Roland are commented on. In this regard, it is also mentioned that in England and France in 1848, the representatives of the highest class of nobles, who participate in state management, began to be called "Pierre". Twelve days. Twelve legendary knights of Charlemagne's ranks were called that. In "The Turpen Chronicles", these twelve heroes, who performed absolutely incredible feats, were famous for their many adventures. [1] Ancient conversations between Don Quixote and Sancho Panza also attract the reader's attention. In this regard, Don Quixote's promise to his friend Sancho as an armourer and governorship are mentioned. The fact that Sancho soon owns imaginary islands and starts a little rulership, and that he leads the island in a way worthy of his wife and children, also motivates him to act in this regard. Notable words and characters are mentioned. Santa Ermandat. Santa Ermandat means holy brotherhood. This name, which unites urban and rural associations, prevails in the whole of Spain in the XV-XIV centuries. The feudal lords make several attempts to destroy Santa Ermanda. However, the association's attention is also starting to increase. These associations of Santa Hermandat, formed by the Catholic check in the beginning of the thirteenth century when the Inquisition intensified and suppressed and suppressed by the Church, create a great reality for Sancho, who thinks that he analyzes the heroism of Don Quixote in the carriage. Ointment also has a small role in this regard. The thread that can be pulled from the rag plays a big role in pressing the wounds in the past. It should not be forgotten that the application of a drug worth at least three reals affects Don Quixote only for those who have received the title of knighthood.

Spirituality is not a concept that appeared yesterday or today, it is a great value that has been living and developing together with our people for centuries. From the day a person is born, until the last moment of his life, he grows up and matures in the values and traditions of the people he belongs to. Even a person who considers himself a stranger to folklore, who is

completely far from the tariff of this term, is formed under the influence of these ancient traditions. Genres of folklore and its inalienable heroes, which are the spiritual wealth of our people, the experience of artistic creativity serve as the main spiritual and artistic source for the creation and development of written literature. In fact, there is probably not a single artist who could not enjoy the oral creativity of the people and was not nourished by its spiritual wealth. Similarly, when we read Isajon Sultan's stories, we see that he effectively used examples of folklore.[2] Sancho warms to Don Quixote's principle of self-treatment with drugs and herbs based on two or three real realities of nature.

Sancho warms to Don Quixote's principle of treating himself with absurd medicines and plants based on two or three real realities of nature. However, Asumbra is depicted as Sancho's death due to a measure of more than two liters of liquid and as a person lying on his stomach within a few hours, even Don Quixote can see his erudition in the play. He recommends his magic medicine to the creator of eighteen thousand worlds, such as "Torah", "Zabur" "Injil" "Koran" and these books. In the course of the work, specific names of monetary units are given, and the misqal-ancient weight measure was used to measure valuable items in the East and Arab countries. The weight of one misqal is equal to one hundred grains of barley or wheat.

"Another web platform for teaching world literature is the quizizz.com resource. It is also possible to conduct classes in the form of a presentation. During the presentation of the lesson, there are several types of questions, tests, questionnaires, and several other types of knowledge testing. The lesson presentation can be colorfully developed in several ways. Pictures, audio files and video images can be added to the presentation. There are many opportunities to test your knowledge. It is possible to create multiple-choice tests, closed-answer questions, answer-writing tests, and picture questions. The teacher creates a task on his computer, and students can do it separately from their mobile devices with Internet access (smartphone, tablet). The web resource also enables collaboration. The quizzes can be organized in the form of a game, and to join the game, students must follow a link and enter a special code. The tasks are the same for all participants, but the sequence of questions is different for each person. The teacher can send the obtained results to an Excel spreadsheet. The teacher has the opportunity not only to create his own tests and quizzes, but also to use a wide library of ready-made tasks. There is also an option to send the created task by email or share it on social networks".[3]

If one grain of barley was equal to 0.4 grams on average in ancient times, today's calculations also cause a big difference. The episodes from the epic "Roland in Love" by the Italian poet Matthieuboyardo, who lived and created in the years 1434-1494, together with his various epics crosses his mind. The heroes and various difficulties that befell him invite him to analyze as well as presented in the works. In this regard, the lover is presented on the basis of the siege of Albarak by Roland.

As a result of Don Quixote's adventures, many events lead to different realities, as presented in the works of medieval and Renaissance literature. In this, mainly, the great adventure and the acquisition of Monbiri's priceless helmet and the conversation between the knight and his squire create the intense events of the sixteenth and seventeenth chapters. The

famous battle between the fearless Diskai and the brave Lamoch is an example of this incident.

In the continuation of the work, how Jines de Pasamonti stole Sancho Panso's donkey and the development of events in this regard in the nineteenth chapter also attract the attention of our readers. Don Quixote, who decided to send a chaperone to Dusilenia of Taboso, expressed his love in every chaperon he sent, as well as going to the charming Dusileny of Taboso. In the battle with the horsemen, Don Quixote is wounded, and Don Quixote blames the squire or his horse for various incidents. His horse tries to resist him several times. In this, their invincibility is presented in this way. The strange incident that happened in the caravanserai and the strange sounds of the caravanserai are used in various stories and tales in the nineteenth and thirty-ninth chapters.

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